

PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF A SFH/NCBFSK COMMUNICATION SYSTEM WITH RATE 1/2 CONVOLUTIONAL CODING IN THE PRESENCE OF PARTIAL-BAND NOISE JAMMING

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Abstract-A performance analysis of a slow frequency-hopped, noncoherent binary frequency-shift keying (SFH/NCBFSK) communication system with rate 1/2 convolutional coding and soft decision Viterbi decoding in the presence of partial-band noise jamming is performed. The effect of additive white Gaussian noise is also considered. The system's performance is severely degraded by partial-band noise jamming. By way of comparison, a system that utilizes hard decision Viterbi decoding and for a system utilizing noise-normalized combining with soft decision Viterbi decoding are examined. In both cases a significant increase in the system's immunity to the effects of partial-band noise jamming is achieved.

I. INTRODUCTION

In this paper, the performance of a slow frequency-hopped, non-coherent binary frequency-shift keying (SFH/NCBFSK) communication system with rate 1/2 convolutional coding and soft decision Viterbi decoding is examined. The system's performance is examined for partial-band noise jamming in addition to additive white Gaussian noise. The analysis of this system is of interest because similar communication systems are currently in use. The resistance of a communication system to jamming is of extreme importance to military communication systems. Since partial-band noise jamming can be a particularly effective jamming scheme, the system's ability to resist the effects of partial-band noise jamming is of particular interest [1].

II. PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

A. Soft Decision Decoding

A SFH/NCBFSK communication system with rate 1/2 convolutional coding and soft decision Viterbi decoding is shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: SFH/NCBFSK Communication System with rate 1/2 convolutional coding and soft decision Viterbi detection

For a communication system that employs convolutional coding with Viterbi decoding, the probability of bit error is upper bounded by [2, 3, 4]

$$P_b < \sum_{d=d_{free}}^{\infty} B_d P_d \quad (1)$$

where B_d is the total number of nonzero information bits in all weight d paths and P_d is the probability of selecting a code word that is a Hamming distance d from the correct code word. For a SFH/NCBFSK communications system with rate 1/2 convolutional coding and soft decision Viterbi decoding in the presence of partial-band noise jamming, P_d is [5, 6, 7]

$$P_d = \sum_{i=0}^d \binom{d}{i} \gamma^i \cdot (1-\gamma)^{d-i} \cdot P_d(i) \quad (2)$$

where γ is the fraction of the spread spectrum bandwidth being jammed, and $P_d(i)$ is the probability of selecting a code word a Hamming distance d from the correct code word given that i of d diversity receptions are jammed. For a NCBFSK system employing convolutional coding and soft decision Viterbi decoding, P_d is equivalent to P_b for a system with d^{th} order diversity. Hence, $P_d(i)$ is given by [5, 6]

$$P_d(i) = \int_0^\infty f_{V_1}(v_1|i) \cdot \left[1 - \int_0^{v_1} f_{V_2}(v_2|i) dv_2 \right] dv_1 \quad (3)$$

where V_1 and V_2 represent the decision variables, and V_{1k} and V_{2k} are random variables that model the output of the two branches of the NCBFSK detector. The probability density functions (pdfs) for the decision variables V_{1k} and V_{2k} are [5]

$$f_{V_{1k}}(v_{1k}) = \frac{1}{2 \cdot \sigma_k^2} \cdot \exp\left[-\frac{(v_{1k} + 2 \cdot A_c^2)}{2 \cdot \sigma_k^2}\right] \quad (4)$$

$$I_0\left(\frac{A_c \cdot \sqrt{2 \cdot v_1}}{\sigma_k^2}\right)$$

and

$$f_{V_{2k}}(v_{2k}) = \frac{1}{2 \cdot \sigma_k^2} \cdot \exp\left(\frac{-v_{2k}}{2 \cdot \sigma_k^2}\right) \quad (5)$$

If we indicate jammed bits and bits which are not jammed by the superscripts (1) and (2), respectively, the pdfs for the decision variables V_1 and V_2 are [5, 6, 7]

$$f_{V_{1i}}(v_1|i) = \left[f_{V_{1k}}^{(1)}(v_{1k}) \right]^{\otimes i} \otimes \left[f_{V_{1k}}^{(2)}(v_{1k}) \right]^{\otimes (d-i)} \quad (6)$$

$$f_{V_{2i}}(v_2|i) = \left[f_{V_{2k}}^{(1)}(v_{2k}) \right]^{\otimes i} \otimes \left[f_{V_{2k}}^{(2)}(v_{2k}) \right]^{\otimes (d-i)} \quad (7)$$

where \otimes indicates convolution. We designate the noise power σ_k^2 for jammed bits as σ_1^2 and non-jammed bits as σ_2^2 , where

$$\sigma_1^2 = \frac{\left(N_0 + \frac{N_J}{\gamma}\right)}{rT_b} \quad (8)$$

and

$$\sigma_2^2 = \frac{N_0}{rT_b} \quad (9)$$

where r is the code rate and T_b is the duration of a bit. Substituting for the pdfs of V_{1k} and V_{2k} and taking the Laplace transforms of (7) and (8), we obtain [5]

$$F_{V_{1i}}(s) = \left[\frac{1}{2 \cdot \sigma_1^2} \cdot \frac{1}{s + \frac{1}{2\sigma_1^2}} \cdot \exp\left(\frac{-A_c^2}{\sigma_1^2} \cdot \frac{s}{s + \frac{1}{2\sigma_1^2}}\right) \right]^i \cdot \left[\frac{1}{2 \cdot \sigma_2^2} \cdot \frac{1}{s + \frac{1}{2\sigma_2^2}} \cdot \exp\left(\frac{-A_c^2}{\sigma_2^2} \cdot \frac{s}{s + \frac{1}{2\sigma_2^2}}\right) \right]^{d-i} \quad (10)$$

and

$$F_{V_{2i}}(s) = \left[\frac{1}{2 \cdot \sigma_1^2 \cdot s + 1} \right]^i \cdot \left[\frac{1}{2 \cdot \sigma_2^2 \cdot s + 1} \right]^{d-i} \quad (11)$$

No simple analytic solutions exist for the inverse Laplace transforms of the above expressions; therefore, the inverse Laplace transforms are determined numerically [5].

B. Hard Decision Decoding

If hard decision Viterbi detection is utilized, P_d in (1) is [2, 3, 4]

$$P_d = \sum_{i=\frac{d+1}{2}}^d \binom{d}{i} \cdot p^i \cdot (1-p)^{d-i} \quad (12)$$

when d is odd, and

$$P_d = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \binom{\frac{d}{2}}{\frac{d}{2}} \cdot p^{\frac{d}{2}} \cdot (1-p)^{\frac{d}{2}} + \sum_{i=\frac{d}{2}+1}^d \binom{d}{i} \cdot p^i \cdot (1-p)^{d-i} \quad (13)$$

when d is even. In (12) and (13), the channel transition probability p is [1, 3]

$$p = \frac{\gamma}{2} \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{rE_b}{2\left(N_0 + \frac{N_J}{\gamma}\right)}\right) + \frac{(1-\gamma)}{2} \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{rE_b}{2N_0}\right) \quad (14)$$

C. Noise-normalization Combining

If a noise-normalized receiver [6] is utilized with soft decision Viterbi decoding, $P_d(i)$ in (3) is [8]

$$P_d(i) = \frac{1}{2^{2d-1}} \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{rE_b}{2} \cdot \left(\frac{i}{N_0 + \frac{N_J}{\gamma}} + \frac{d-i}{N_0}\right)\right) \quad (15)$$

$$\sum_{n=0}^{d-1} c_n \left(\frac{rE_b}{2} \cdot \left(\frac{i}{N_0 + \frac{N_J}{\gamma}} + \frac{d-i}{N_0}\right)\right)^n$$

where c_n is

$$c_n = \frac{1}{n!} \cdot \sum_{m=0}^{d-1-n} \binom{2d-1}{m} \quad (16)$$

III. NUMERICAL RESULTS

A. Soft Decision Decoding

The probability of bit error (P_b) was calculated numerically using (1)-(3). For the conventional receiver utilizing soft decision Viterbi detection, the pdf of V_1 was calculated by taking the inverse Laplace transform of (10) numerically. The integral of the pdf of V_2 contained in the bracketed term of (3) is calculated by taking the inverse Laplace transform of (11) multiplied by $1/s$; i.e.,

$$\frac{1}{s} \cdot \left[\frac{1}{2 \cdot \sigma_1^2 \cdot s + 1} \right]^i \cdot \left[\frac{1}{2 \cdot \sigma_2^2 \cdot s + 1} \right]^{d-i}$$

$P_d(i)$ is then calculated from (3) using a Simpson's rule numerical integration [9].

The analysis was performed for two different constraint length (v) codes, $v=3$ and $v=7$. Four separate cases of partial-band jamming were examined: $\gamma = 1.0$, $\gamma = 0.1$, $\gamma = 0.01$, and $\gamma = 0.001$. The performance of a conventional receiver using soft decision detection is shown in Figs. 2 and 3 for $v = 3$ and $v = 7$, respectively. From the results shown in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3, it is evident that partial-band noise jamming is extremely effective in degrading the performance of this receiver.

We hypothesize that soft decision decoding in combination with linear combining actually results in performance degradation when partial-band noise jamming is present. This is because with soft decision decoding a single jammed hop can completely dominate the decision statistic.

This receiver's low immunity to partial-band noise jamming is a result of the lack of the use of side information. By using linear combining and soft decision decoding, the jammed receptions dominate the non-jammed receptions in the overall decision statistic, resulting in poor system performance. If side information is used the system's performance will dramatically improve with regard to its ability to resist the effects of

partial-band noise jamming. To demonstrate this, the performance of a noise-normalized SFH/NCBFSK receiver with rate 1/2 convolutional coding and soft decision Viterbi decoding is also presented.

Figure 2: Performance of a conventional SFH/NCBFSK receiver with rate 1/2 convolutional coding and soft decision Viterbi decoding, for $v = 3$

Figure 3: Performance of a conventional SFH/NCBFSK receiver with rate 1/2 convolutional coding and soft decision Viterbi decoding, for $v = 7$

Since soft decision detection is most commonly implemented using multi-bit quantization, we speculate that the performance of a system utilizing quantization will have improved performance in defeating partial-band jamming as compared to the system using ideal soft decision detection. This is because the quantization limits the values that the output variables can take prior to combining. This should result in increased system robustness with regards to defeating partial-band jamming. Consequently, we expect hard decision decoding to actually outperform soft decision decoding when partial-band noise jamming is present since with hard decision decoding the effect of jammed hops is limited. This

hypothesis is examined by analyzing the performance of a SFH/NCBFSK communication system using rate 1/2 convolutional coding and hard decision Viterbi decoding.

B. Noise-normalization Combining

The probability of bit error was also calculated for the noise-normalized receiver. The analysis was performed by implementing (1) and (2). $P_d(i)$ was calculated using (15) and substituted into (2). The analysis was performed for the same values of v and γ as the conventional receiver. The results are displayed in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5, for $v = 3$ and $v = 7$, respectively.

Figure 4: Performance of a noise-normalized SFH/NCBFSK receiver with rate 1/2 convolutional coding and soft decision Viterbi decoding, for $v = 3$

With the use of noise-normalization, we achieved a significant increase in the system's ability to limit the effects of partial-band noise jamming. This increased resistance to partial-band jamming forces a potential hostile jammer to adopt barrage noise jamming, causing the hostile jammer to spread the energy of the jamming source over the entire bandwidth of the communication system. This effectively increases E_b/N_J .

C. Hard Decision Decoding

P_b was also calculated when hard decision Viterbi decoding was used. The calculations of P_b were performed by implementing (1). P_d was calculated by using (12) when d was odd and (13) when d was even. The probability of bit error for independent diversity receptions was calculated using (14). The results for $v = 3$ and $v = 7$ are shown in Fig. 6 and Fig. 7, respectively.

Figure 5: Performance of a noise-normalized SFH/NCBFSK receiver with rate 1/2 convolutional coding and soft decision Viterbi detection, for $v = 7$

The use of hard decision Viterbi decoding demonstrates a significant improvement in its ability to withstand partial-band noise jamming as compared to the conventional receiver utilizing soft decision Viterbi decoding. However, the lower asymptotic limit for P_b when the hard decision Viterbi detection is used is greater than the lower asymptotic limit for P_b when soft decision Viterbi detection is used. Also, for the case of barrage noise jamming, soft decision Viterbi decoding has approximately 3 dB better performance than that for hard decision Viterbi decoding. This result is expected [2, 3, 4]. As in the previous cases examined, the receiver utilizing the constraint length seven code outperformed the constraint length three code.

Figure 6: Performance of a conventional SFH/NCBFSK receiver with rate 1/2 convolutional coding and hard decision Viterbi decoding, for $v = 3$

Figure 7: Performance of a conventional SFH/NCBFSK receiver with rate 1/2 convolutional coding and hard decision Viterbi decoding, $v = 7$

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The performance of a SFH/NCBFSK communications system employing rate 1/2 convolutional coding and soft decision Viterbi decoding is severely degraded by partial-band noise jamming. The two constraint lengths examined showed that although the stronger code provides a lower asymptotic limit for P_b , it does not provide a significant increase in immunity to partial-band jamming. This susceptibility to partial-band noise jamming is believed to be due to the linear combining of the jammed and non-jammed receptions in the decoder. The linear combining resulted in the jammed receptions having the same weight as non-jammed receptions, allowing the jammed receptions to dominate the decision statistic.

The noise-normalized receiver provides improved performance in its ability to withstand partial-band noise jamming. It also provides the same lower asymptotic limit as the conventional receiver using soft decision Viterbi detection. For the receiver with hard decision Viterbi detection, an increased resistance to partial-band noise jamming is realized. When either hard decision Viterbi decoding is utilized or noise-normalized combining is used with soft decision Viterbi decoding, a potential jammer is forced to adopt a barrage noise jamming scheme in order to be most effective in jamming the signal.

The use of side information to de-emphasize the jammed hops was illustrated to significantly increase the system's immunity to partial-band jamming. Hard decision detection was also shown to significantly improve the system's immunity to partial-band jamming because the effect of an error due to a jammed reception was limited to a single bit.

Most often, ideal soft decision detection is not utilized in real world systems, but multi-level quantization is used. We hypothesize that the use of three-bit quantization will improve the performance of the system analyzed in this paper. By using three-bit quantization, we can achieve increased immunity to partial-band jamming analogous to that exhibited by the system using hard decision detection. Also, the use of multi-level quantization should allow for the lower asymptotic limit to be at or near the asymptotic limit obtained when ideal soft decision detection is used as well as provide improved performance in the case of barrage noise jamming.

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